

The Influence of High-commitment Human Resource Management on Unethical Pro-Organizational Behavior: The Moderating Role of the Perceived Organizational Support in Nigeria

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Abstract: This study seeks to investigate the influence of high-commitment HRM (HCHRM) on unethical pro-organizational behaviours (UPB), with the moderating role of perceived organizational support (POS) in Nigeria. The study finds that if workers think they will be compensated for unethical behaviour, they would more certainly engage in it. Employees who have historically been rewarded for immoral behaviour are most likely to engage in it again in the future. Although UPB can help organizations in the near run, it is not a long-term development strategy for organizations. Because it violates ethics, it will ultimately hurt the organization's goals and reduce the business's ability to compete in the long run. Perceived organizational support and high commitment human resource management are examples of productive constructs that may have an impact on unethical behaviour. As a result, the company needs to take action to stop employees from adopting UPB.

Keywords: High-commitment Human Relations Management; Unethical Pro-organizational behaviors; Perceived Organizational Support.

I. Introduction

Employees frequently misuse their influence for personal gain, sacrificing the organization's interests for their own. Researchers have paid close attention to this type of unethical behaviour [1]. Because unethical action breaches norms and disturbs social order, it will hurt society to varying degrees. As a result, researchers' study has focused on the mechanism that causes such conduct in order to avoid and limit its recurrence. In many circumstances, however, individuals engage in such unethical action not for themselves, but for the benefit of the leadership or business. Employees, for instance, misrepresent the company's financial status to appease the boss, inflate the advantages of products to customers to boost sales, and conceal product flaws to protect the organization's interests. Positive organizational elements like conscientious leadership and organizational support may serve as significant inducements for unethical action, according to Umphress et al [2]. Because these favourable elements may boost their allegiance and dedication to the firm, employees may compromise their social interests for the organization's gain and subsequently engage in immoral behaviour. UPB was used to describe this altruistic immoral conduct (unethical pro-organizational behavior). Many academics have begun to perform more in-depth studies on this unique immoral behaviour in order to investigate its mechanism and affecting elements.

High levels of commitment (HRM) and perceived organizational support (POS), on the other hand, have been proven to influence UPB. HRM is a set of human resource policies that have the ability to improve the performance of a business. These rules are largely intended to improve employee attitudes and behaviour, improve customer service quality, increase labour turnover, and eliminate negative aspects that may exist among workers, such as absenteeism. The degree to which employees believe their organization recognises their efforts, cares about their well-being, and, most importantly, satisfies their socio-emotional needs is referred to as perceived organizational support (POS) [3]. Workers tend to work better when they receive earned incentives and preferred treatment, hence POS is commonly perceived as the organization's contribution to a good reciprocity dynamic with employees [3]. The bulk of UPBs in

Nigeria are affected by highly dedicated HR procedures, and they are greatly influenced by employee POS[4]. the employers' commitment to the group[5].

Employees also use their position to maximise their own profit while disregarding the interests of the firm. Although immoral behaviour defies norms and disturbs social order, the cultural danger varies in severity. As a result, researchers have focused on the generation process in order to avoid and mitigate certain behaviors. However, in some cases, such immoral behaviour is not the fault of the individual, but of the management or organization. Workers utilize deceptive evidence to overestimate their financial situation, exaggerate the advantages to customers of the items in order to maximise revenues, and conceal product flaws in order to protect the organization's interests. According to Umphress et al.[2], many positive organizational concerns such as ethical management and corporate support may nonetheless entail major benefits for immoral behaviour. Due to these beneficial influences that can enhance the identity and loyalty of workers to the company, employees may surrender social values and thus conduct themselves in an ethical way. This altruistic and immoral conduct was described as unethical UPB [2].

Because the conception of nonethical pro-organizational conduct overturned the view of prior research, academics have after their presentation gained interest. Many researchers have started to research this unique immoral behaviour in greater detail and examine the function and forces that affect it. Some studies have discussed how UPB is influenced by different factors such as spiritual [2,6]; mental factors, thoughts about job[7], and so on. The UPB has also shown a strong effect on organizational considerations such as the identity of organizations [2], the patronage of organizations (Alexandra, 2012) or the ethical environment of organization[8]. Leadership, including ethical leadership [9] and transformative leadership, has also been shown to have important effects [10]. Furthermore, ex-change leadership subordinates have also been proved necessary for the UPB to be implemented by its employees[8,11].

Although unethical pro-organizational behaviour has led to a wide-ranging analysis by historians, it is clear that few studies and comparatively little literature on the impact of highly committed human resource management in nonethical, pro-organizational behaviour can be consulted.

In organizations, HRM officers are saddled with the responsibility of motivating staff to function optimally towards the attainment of set goals. These goals boil down to making a profit for the organization. In most cases, HRM officers are highly committed and are determined to do whatever it takes to achieve results, even though ethical standards are compromised. The lack of ethics among HRM officers in private and public organizations remains a terrible crime and bridge of trust. Increasingly, employees in organizations are incentivized to work against ethics in order to be considered pro-organization. Every citizen is needed by legislation and personal values to prioritize the safety of others over personal or organizational objectives. However, in cases when an organization's work endangers human welfare and existence, workers continue to engage in illegal work practices despite being aware of the risks since the HCHRM team has programmed them to do so. The pervasive breach of ethics in Nigerian big businesses in the name of perceived organizational support raises serious questions. Citizens, investors, and the government are the most vulnerable in this situation. In an appraisal of executive honesty, Zhang et al.[12] argues that employees have created a pattern of logic that inadvertently promotes unethical behaviour. Large firms often participate in internal trade to siphon money into their coffers. If left unchecked, these UPBs would undoubtedly cause excessive harm to clients, company investors, and the economy; therefore, this research is on the effect of HCHRM on UPB in Nigerian enterprises and employees with the moderating role of POS. based on the forgoing this study seeks to investigate the influence of High commitment HRM on Unethical Pro-organizational behaviours, with the moderating role of perceived organizational support in Nigeria.

II. Theoretical Background and Research Hypotheses

2.1 High-commitment HRM and UPBs

Madhurima et al. [13] claim that the HRM division can accurately evaluate the effects of UPBs on the business. There is a chance that this will go unnoticed, leading to unfavourable outcomes. The ultimate demise of numerous businesses in the twenty-first century serves to confirm that UPBs are common in the workplace.

At NNPC, there are high-commitment HRMs in charge of the various UPBs that have been noticed across the board. As workers frequently participate in extra-procedural activities to advance the "well-being" of the organizations for which they work[14], employee POS in Nigeria also plays a vital role in this. The presence of high commitment HRM that encourages personal accountability for performance influences the occurrence of these UPBs, whereas businesses in Nigeria may be pressured to engage in immoral pro-organizational practices in order to meet financial targets within certain time periods.

There are two primary parts to UPBs. The first is that UPB is wicked and in no way complies with moral or legal standards. In other words, commission behaviour is defined under UPB as falsifying stock value numbers and figures, illegally altering manufacture and production dates, and other similar actions are done with the intent to deceive the organization's clients or other third parties. UPB frequently covers omission behavior, which occurs when any risks associated with the products are not listed in order to conceal their hazardous nature. These mistakes frequently entail neglecting to accurately describe the defective products to customers. The advantage of the behaviour to the group and the requirement for a much higher level of command make up UPB's second dimension. A UPB is immoral behaviour that benefits the group as a whole. It is critical to note that UPB ultimately causes organizational harm, even if employees may not immediately recognise the effect [13]. Think about employers that change company records to give a better impression than they actually do. An external audit may reveal employees who are certified professionals, such

authorised procurement officers, and cause them to lose their reputation. Additionally, the organization may face severe fines from judicial authorities following the publishing of the reports by external auditors. In other circumstances, the fine may even be the same as how much the organization might earn in a year. The worst aspect of UPBs is that the brand is most likely to lose the trust and loyalty of its customers.

The majority of people think that businesses who deceive their customers are still capable of poisoning them in order to generate money. Who would desire a relationship with such a business? Businesses can only safeguard themselves after being found using UPBs by publishing reports denouncing the behaviour and attributing it to specific employees, who are then either arrested or killed as soon as these reports are published. Such behaviour gives devoted customers the impression that it is just one of the unfortunate things that can happen to any business, and they are likely to accept their mistakes. Any business that wishes to be released from the restrictions set by UPB should also be ready to prove to customers that they are more idealistic and that the calibre of their products is higher than that of their competitors.

In order to stay in business and make significant profits, businesses in Nigeria are increasingly turning to unlawful methods, with MTN and NNPC at the top of the list. Any way you look at it, unethical corporate behaviour is shamefully common in today's society. The practice of discharging toxic chemical wastes into waterways, overcharging the government for Medicaid services, overcharging customers for services, among other alarming practices, are just a few examples of how they manifest themselves.

Taken as a whole, the current research suggests:

H1. High commitment human resource management is positively related to UPB

2.2 The moderating role of perceived organizational behaviour POS

POS is used by HRM when it wants to predict the level of employee commitment. Employee perceptions of organizational support are influenced by the company's unique rules and employee treatment practices [3]. As a result, perceived organizational support includes both good and negative beliefs and behaviours of employees in reaction to how they are treated at work, including whether their boss shows respect for them and values them for their contributions to the team (Vance, 2016). Organizational support denotes that an employer prioritizes its workers' pleasure and well-being, whereas perceived organization support denotes that staff members are aware of what their employer does for them, feel secure, and have a sense of support from the company [15].

Since it illustrates the employer-employee relationship, the importance of perceived organizational support must be exaggerated. There have been studies on the effects of perceived organizational support on employee commitment, according to a review of the literature [16]. According to Grisly's[17] research, employees who feel that their organization has their back show more organizational dedication, and their emotional commitment increases. Undoubtedly, this would lead to a rise in UPB. Workers are more devoted to their group, in Mohammed's[18] opinion, since they receive the assistance, they need and can observe it at work. These ideas allow us to draw the conclusion that employees' views of organizational support affect how well they perform their job obligations. They have a high turnover rate at work, which is done more willingly, and they place a high value on their contributions to the organization's goals, which leads to the development of a greater UPB. Employees' desire to participate in UPB may be increased by organizations with HCHRM strategies; in addition, employees with a high level of POS will still feel more at ease performing UPB. The capacity of an employee to carry out UPB is improved when POS is high throughout the organization; on the other hand, when POS is low within the organization, this may indicate that the employee is not working hard enough to win the organization's favour.

H2. Perceived Organizational Support (POS) moderates the positive effect of high-commitment human resource management on unethical pro-organizational behaviour, resulting in a solid alliance between high-commitment human resource management and UPB for workers with greater POS.

Figure 1: The theoretical model

III. Research Design

The term "research design" relates to the overall research approach employed in a study. As a result, the research employed an ex-post facto design, with a survey instrument used to collect main data for the research. The investigative technique used in this study included gathering information from a subset of a population of interest while remaining detached enough to imply objectivity and reliability in the research process. According to De Vaus [19], the study design is a framework that assures that the evidence collected successfully answers the study issue or question.

3.1. Data Collection

A survey was used to obtain data in Nigeria. The data gathering procedure was critical since it allowed for the acquisition of a huge amount of information in a short amount of time. The questionnaire's subject varies as well. Questionnaires have no time limits, especially when given by mail, email, or internet. Respondents are kept anonymous in the context of the study. The poll delivers useful statistics, and this data should be utilised to build new strategies for tracking audience behaviours and habits. The study's findings greatly simplify analysis and visualisation. Statistics should be easily quantifiable in order to compare and contrast with other types of research. The questionnaire can easily be translated into other languages to improve comprehension and response rate. A total of 300 questionnaires were delivered to Nigeria by email, and a group of taught individuals and colleagues assisted in printing and distributing the questionnaires to workers employed in various businesses in Nigeria, mostly MTN and NNPC. The response was compiled after the copies of the questionnaire were distributed, and approximately 270 workers attended and returned the completed questionnaires. The copies of the completed questionnaires were delivered from Nigeria to China through DHL air freight delivery, which cost money to get to the destination in China.

3.2. Measures

High-commitment HRM: The scale is from McClean and Collins [20]. High-commitment human resource processes, employee endeavour, and business performance: examining the ramifications of human resource procedures among employee communities of professional services companies. Fifteen objects include, for example, promotion from within rather than from without (promotion from within); assessment of team performance rather than individual performance (appraisal squad); and feedback for growth rather than assessment (appraisal development). Cronbach's Alpha was 0.813 for this scale's reliability.

UPB is adapted from Umphress et al. [2], such as "I would embellish the truth if it would benefit my organization in order to enhance its reputation", "I would embellish facts about my company's goods or services to consumers and clients if doing so would benefit my business", and "I would keep unfavourable information about my business or its goods from consumers and clients if doing so would benefit my organization". For this scale, the coefficient is 0.432.

POS is adapted from Eisenberger et al. [21]. For example, "Management shows very little concern for me", "Management is concerned with my overall job satisfaction", "Management really cares about my well-being". The coefficient α for this scale 0.195

Control variables include employees' sex, age, marital status, qualification and tenure. The coefficient α for this scale 0.56

The variables including POS, UPB and HCHRM were all assessed using a five-point Likert-type scale (1= Strongly agree; 5 = Strongly disagree)

3.3 Analytic Strategy

Three phases were involved in the economic interpretation. First, a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted using Amos 22.0 to evaluate the convergent and discriminant validity of each factor. In this work, a series of CFAs were performed using maximum likelihood estimation, and the model fit was evaluated using the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), incremental fit index (IFI), root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA), comparative fit index (CFI) for the entire model.

Second, the poll data were randomly arranged before being subjected to Harman's one-factor test in order to minimize common method bias.

Third, in accordance with Dawson (2014), we used a four-step hierarchical multiple regression analysis to test our theories. The control factors (employee sex, age, academic qualification, and tenure) were joined first, accompanied by High-commitment Human Resource Management in the second step. POS are added at the next step.

In the fourth step, the multiplicative interactive word between HCHRM and POS was added. Specifically, several statistical treatments were carried out for the interaction effect. The predictor (High commitment HRM) and moderator (Perceived organizational support) were mean-centered in this research, and the two factors were multiplied to create an interaction term. This research attempted to eliminate non-essential multicollinearity and increase the interpretability of the predictor variable's first term in the analysis findings by doing so. This research used Aiken and West's [22] procedure to more explicitly quantify the area of importance of the moderating effect in addition to the method of verifying the relevance of the moderation effect based on the above and below 1SD in the slope difference test. SPSS 23.0 was used for the studies.

IV. Regressions Analysis

4.1. Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Matrix of Variables

A sample size of 263 were used of the study. Among all the respondents, 44.2% of them were female. The respondents' mean age was 30.49 (SD=0.49) with ages ranging from 18 to 62. Marital status shows that 53 percent were unmarried while 46% were married. Annual income shows a mean annual income of 462140.39, (SD=414543.463) and educational attainment of Junior college or below being 19.2%, Bachelor degree 59.6 %, and Master degree and above 9.1%. Among the respondents reported, General Manager was 16.2%, Middle-level Manager 15.5%, Senior Management 61.5%. on the number of people worked with (tenure) the mean value was 25.615, (SD=46.8295).

Table 1 presents the means, standard deviations and zero-order Pearson correlations of all key variables. As indicated, High Commitment Human Resource Management was found to be positively correlated with UPB (r =0.481, p<0.001). There was a significant positive relationship between Perceived Organizational Support and UPB (r=0.456, p<0.000). High Commitment Human Resource Management was found to have a highly significant positive relationship with POS (r =0.948, p<0.000). Gender (r=0.011, p>0.429) and Educational attainment (r =0.059, p>0.184) show an insignificant positive relationship with UPB, Annual Income (r =-0.098, p<0.058) shows an insignificant negative relationship with UPB. However, Age (r =0.125, p<0.021), Marital Status (r =0.129, p<0.018), Position (r=0.113, p<0.038) and Tenure (r=0.230, p<0.000) have significant positive relationship with UPB.

Table 1: Means Standard Deviations and Correlations

Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1. UPB	3.040	0.643	-								
2. HCHRM	3.146	0.627	0.481**	-							
3. POS	3.086	0.804	0.456**	.948**	-						
4. Gender	0.555	0.498	0.011	-.027	-.079	-					
5. Age	30.494	7.238	0.125*	.250**	.258**	.159**	-				
6.marital status	0.462	0.500	0.129*	.205**	.216**	-.046	.494**	-			
7.Annual Income	462140.39	414543.463	-0.098	.066	-	.232**	.415**	.363**	-		
8.Educational Attainment	1.884	0.557	0.059	0.087	0.066	0.155**	0.352**	0.298**	0.370*	-	
9. Position	2.476	0.788	0.113*	0.159*	0.104	-0.131*	-0.112*	0.078	0.003	0.017	-
10. Tenure	25.615	46.8305	0.230**	0.119*	0.105*	-0.015	0.203**	0.113*	0.041	0.080	0.158**

Table 2 presents the results of the hierarchical multiple regression analysis. High-commitment human resource management is positively related to UPB. The results demonstrated that High-commitment human resource management was significantly positively related to UPB ($\beta = 0.446, p < 0.000$), supporting H1. Also, it can be seen that the model variables relating to HCHRM practices contributed to 30% of the variance in UPB (R^2 value = 0.298). The relationship between perceived organizational support and UPB ($\beta = 0.214, p > 0.267$), show a significant positive relationship with UPB. Also, it can be seen that the model variables relating to POS contributed to 30.2% of the variance in UPB (R^2 value = 0.302).

Perceived organizational support POS moderates the positive influence of High-commitment human resource management on Unethical Pro-organization Behaviour such that the relationship between high-commitment human resource management and UPB are strong for employees with higher POS. As shown in Table 2, the Interaction term HCHRM * POS proved to be significantly related to UPB ($\beta = 1.247, p < 0.05$). this indicates that perceived organizational support, moderated by HCHRM contributes to about 32% changes in Unethical pro-organizational behaviours (R^2 value = 0.317).

Table 2: Hierarchical regression Results(DV=UPB)

Variables	Step1	Step2	Step3	Step4
Gender	0.067	0.079	.096	0.111
Age	0.087	-0.042	-0.039	-0.039
Marital Status	0.164*	0.124	0.121	0.117
Annual Income	-0.278***	-0.242***	-0.253***	-0.249***
Educational attainment	0.073	0.073	0.076	0.068
Position	0.056	-0.021**	-0.008	-0.011
Tenure	0.182**	0.174**	0.175**	0.175
HCHRM		0.446***	0.242	-0.209
POS			0.214	-0.589
HCHRM * POS				1.247*
R ²	0.124	0.298	0.302	0.317
Δ R ²	0.124	0.174	0.004	0.014
F	4.236	51.545	1.239	4.289

Notes: n= 263. UPB(Unethical pro-organizational behaviours); HCHRM(High-commitment Human Resource Management); POS(Perceived Organizational Support). *** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$

V. Conclusion

5.1 Discussion of Findings

This study investigated the influence of High commitment HRM on Unethical Pro-organizational behaviours, with the moderating role of perceived organizational support in Nigeria using the NNPC and MTN.

Results of the statistical analyses revealed that High commitment human resource management is positively and statistically significant to Unethical pro-organisational behaviours. As a result, this suggests that the personnel that receive organizational support had a significant positive promotion influence on UPB. Employees who value job design, participation in decision making, training and development, pay for accomplishment, a high level of pay, and performance evaluation for employee reward and performance may impact workers' morale, encouraging them to conduct UPB. With a correlation of up to 48% between high commitment human resource management and unethical organizational behaviours, there is a robust association between the two. The conclusions of this research support Matherne and Litchfield's [23] contention that workers with good organizational emotional devotion are more likely to make UPB for the benefit of the group, and that this relation is shaped by personal moral identity. This is also consistent with Graham et al. 's[24] conclusions, who studied the effect of leadership style on workers' UPB under agriculture regulation and found that inspiring and charismatic transformational leaders encouraged higher levels of UPB. Furthermore, Hassan and Mahmood [25] discovered that HRM tactics have a positive impact on employees' organizational commitment. In addition, the findings agree with that of Gigol[26] who published research on the impact of authentic leadership on immoral pro-organizational behaviour: the function of job participation as an intermediary. The research study aims to demonstrate the interdependence of leadership, job commitment, and unethical pro-organizational action. The paper described job commitment as a bridge between supervisory leadership and dishonest pro-organizational action by subordinates. According to the poll, authentic leadership encourages subordinates to indulge in dishonest pro-organizational conduct. Practical ramifications were created, such as increased incorporation of ethics into organizational core values by company boards and a focus on studying business ethics in colleges and MBA programmes.

According to the conclusions of this research, perceived organizational support (POS) moderates the positive effect of high-commitment human resource management on unethical pro-organization behaviour. According to the findings of this research, the association between high commitment human resource management and UPB is good for workers with greater POS. When workers have high expectations about how much the company values their endeavours and cares about their well-being, high commitment human resource management has a huge impact on their proclivity to unethical pro-organization behaviour. This is consistent with Eisenberger et al (1990) contention that a worker's perception of how an organization values him/her may be pivotal in picking behaviours that benefit the group. Also, the findings of this study are consistent with Allen & Wayne[27], which state that positive, beneficial actions taken by

the organization and/or its representatives (referred to as donors) aimed at employees would contribute to the establishment of high-quality exchange relationships, which would create obligatory exchange relationships. UPB is one way for an employee to "repay" the donor's treatment (benefits, opportunities, and other inducements).

However, this research contradicts Alexandra's[28] findings, which showed strong negative associations between self-rated UPB and perceived organizational support, as well as overall justice perceptions. This seems to imply that while workers feel greater levels of systemic support and justice in the workplace, they are less likely to indulge in immoral activities that benefit the group. The basis for this distinct submission is due to his field of research or the nature of the organization used for the research.

5.2 Theoretical Contribution

Our findings have significant consequences for future study. First, existing research has done little to empirically investigate UPB. According to some theoretical work, employers may participate in unethical behaviour to benefit their companies. This study expands on previous findings by providing empirical evidence on the effect of High Commitment Human Resource Management on Unethical Pro-Organizational Behaviour: The Moderating Role of Perceived Organizational Support.

Future study is required to fully comprehend the innate complexities of UPB. Along these lines, we advise researchers to pay close attention to workers' behavioural motivations (i.e., to hurt, assist, and/or only benefit themselves) and to investigate other antecedents and possible impacts.

Second, our findings say that constructs often thought to be productive (such as High Commitment Human Resource Management and Perceived Organizational Support) may affect unethical behaviour.

Concurrently, our findings may point to an overarching systemic culture that encourages unethical behaviour. That means, if workers think they will be compensated for unethical behaviour, they would more certainly engage in it. These assertions are backed by social learning theory[29], which states that individuals learn what is called appropriate job behaviour (even immoral behaviour) by observing salient role models (e.g., managers, coworkers, peers) and through personal experience. Employees who witness others being rewarded for unethical behaviour may see these actions as acceptable and participate in such behaviour. Employees who have historically been rewarded for immoral behaviour are most likely to engage in it again in the future.

5.3 Practical Implications

This study's theoretical model and empirical findings may have some practical consequences for organizations. Although UPB can help companies in the short term, it is not favourable to organizational growth in the long run. Because of the violation of ethics, it will definitely undermine the organization's interests and weaken the entity's long-term viability. As a result, the organization must take steps to prevent employees from implementing UPB.

Businesses should foster an ethically sound environment and an ethical organizational culture. Organizations should strengthen the development of a rule-based ethical climate, further formulate pertinent rules and regulations, codes of behavior such as industry ethics and professional ethics, and necessitate employees to implement them in order to incentivize employees to repay the organization for helping others in a proper and ethical way. This will prevent self-interested ethical climate from inducing employees to implement UPB.

Leaders should consistently raise their moral standards, and organizations should do the same. Leaders should provide a good example for their followers since traits like transformational leadership, servant leadership, ethical leadership, etc., may persuade workers to apply UPB, which has certain undesirable repercussions. Leaders should not overlook, consent to, or even assist workers who are proven to benefit the company in an unethical way. Instead, they should build a strong system of moral incentives and penalties, swiftly and effectively regulate UPB, and include ethical factors in performance evaluation.

The organization should pay attention to employees' moral cognition and improve their moral level. Employees with low moral standards are more likely to engage in UPB, so organization should concern the moral level of employees and organize relevant training to change the unethical moral cognition of employees from the source, guide employees to help organization by acting ethically, instead of actions that harm organization and themselves.

According to Miao et al.[9], the results of this survey indicate that top-level management can develop standards of ethics that specifically define what is and is not appropriate in an organization. A code of ethics should be aligned with an organization's strategy and the ideals it promotes. This would demonstrate a direct conflict with the organization's goals and prohibit the usage of dishonest activities in their pursuit.

Despite the fact that business ethics courses are available for MBA students, they are seldom taken. They should be made mandatory and delivered in the context of hands-on instruction [26]. This will help reduce the incidence of UPB in workplace. The same is true for corporate and marketing classes at the university level. Finally, the concept of environmental management in the area of ethical action in daily business work should be spread.

5.4 Limitation and Future Research Directions

Although the study added the aforementioned to the body of knowledge, it also had certain limitations. First, the two major organizations with excellent compensation packages provided the data for this study. Therefore, it may be difficult to extrapolate the findings to other smaller organizations. Further investigation in several organizations with various cultures and beliefs that are likely to have an impact on the study's variables is necessary to confirm the findings..

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